

Script of Instructive video. Scenario 2

Spanish

Posteriormente se le presentará una segunda situación en la que asumimos que el escenario por COVID-19 se torna más serio y las escuelas cierran nuevamente. Puede seleccionar aquellas medidas de reapertura de escuelas y medidas de salud en este ámbito que le aconsejaría al gobierno implementar.

Translation into English

You will later be shown with a second situation in which we assume that the COVID-19 scenario becomes more serious, and schools are closed again. You can select those school reopening measures and health measures that you would advise the government to implement